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“WHY DO WASTE MATERIALS STILL EXIST SOMEWHERE IN SPACE?”

Where are you going? Do you want to escape? Never! Never ever do that!

Garbage is everywhere and anywhere. It's like weeds, the unwanted or undesirable plants, which have no profit at all, according to most of us. Are we really right in saying so? We do not know that it will be converted into other useful things, where there's profit and more beneficial materials. Segregation is extremely important not only by making our world livable but also for earning money. Segregation of waste materials has been legally and strictly implemented. But why has it seemed unimplemented? Let's take a closer look and dissect the root cause of it.

Try to observe and check out the trash cans distributed by concerned individuals or entities. Can we read biodegradable and non-biodegradable words posted there? Try to inspect inside each of it. What can you see and observe? Yes, no segregation at all takes place. What's happening? Let's cite some possible and real happenings and situations. Firstly, some individuals just ignore the written words. They never even read where waste should be thrown properly. Secondly, they don't even care what they are holding for as long as they can just throw it. Thirdly, the area where trash cans are placed is not managed well. Lastly, somebody, possibly, couldn't understand what biodegradable and non-biodegradable wastes. Human attitude aggravates the situation. If only we knew how to discipline ourselves, only then would we be free of this perennial problem. Let us check ourselves, if we are adding to or lessening this worsening malady.

For better understanding, let us first define the two terms so that we can better understand what we will do to get rid of this rubbish. Biodegradable waste is used to describe materials that decompose through the actions of bacteria, fungi, and other living organisms, such as kitchen food scraps, garden waste, paper and eggshells, human and animal wastes, and cardboard. Non-biodegradable materials take a long time or never decompose. It cannot be degraded or completely destroyed, such as metal cans, bottles, toxic chemicals, plastic products, metal scraps, glass, and many more. These things are only the basic terms that we need to know, but who are the responsible individuals to disseminate this information to all? We are old enough to be taught by this, but I think there must be reinforcement from concerned authorities. Officials of every community have the sole responsibility to manage this kind of inconvenient situation. Some communities have waste management code but it's still useless if don't know about it, and another injustice is punishing through the collection of fines to those who violated the code. Not all people are aware of this in their respective communities. I swear, it is because of a lack of information, drive, or campaign.

Therefore, my challenge for everybody is that let us move peacefully. Do not just wait for the government to make the first move. Be a good influence on others. Be a role model in short. If we see garbage scattered everywhere, make an initiative. Calling also the attention of different officials of various communities, especially national officials, to be environmentalists themselves. You are being looked up to, so be a role model too. Do not wait for the insulting words of concerned individuals to be thrown up before taking action. The only thing that we are asking for is the effective and strict implementation of such a policy, and following up after.

